

PATIKANA

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this work is my own and has not been submitted to this or any other university for the award of any degree or diploma. To the best of my knowledge and belief, this work contains no material previously published or written by another person except where due acknowledgement and reference has been made.

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Signature: _____

Date: _____

APPROVAL

The project proposal of Mary Anna Sadimba was reviewed and approved by the following:

David Kirop

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Date:

DEDICATION

My appreciation goes to my supervisor, Mr. David Kirop, for keeping me on my toes and noting whenever there was a need for making corrections.

Mr. Paul Mwaniki, for availing me the needful resources which guided me in arranging my work.

Thank you, sir.

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ABSTRACT

In a day and age where automation is the buzzword, security cannot be left behind. We have security equipment including, but not limited to CCTVs, scanners, padlocks and detectors. Under detectors, there are infrared occupancy detectors, smoke detectors, carbon monoxide detectors among many others. Notice, all these detectors respond by reacting to the agent, no aspect of visualizing. Patikana is a model that will detect items getting into or out of a building as trained, utilizing the capabilities of computer vision. It will be trained on the items that need to be in a particular building, say computers in a laboratory. With the devices labelled, it will restrict the movement of devices out of the building. My purpose for this study is to enhance the security of items within an institution. The population I will be studying will be the Riara University students with the university as the pilot premise.

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DEFINITION OF TERMS

Annotate - Is to recognize data that is presented in various formats like video, text, or images.

Cell – Is a holder for code to be run by the kernel of a notebook, in this case Google Colaboratory notebook. It can also hold commands which must be accompanied by an exclamation mark or percent sign at the beginning for them to be run, for example `!pip install -qr requirements.txt, %cd yolov5`

Computer vision – A scientific field dealing with enabling computers to understand digital images or videos.

Epoch - This is the number of times an algorithm goes through a whole dataset.

Ground truth – Refers to how accurate the classification of the training set is for techniques like supervised learning.

Human vision – Sight that humans get while using their eyes.

Patikana – The computer vision object detection model is a Swahili word that means found out.

TensorBoard – Is the platform that visualizes a model's graphs, in this case Patikana, in order to aid in its optimization, understanding and debugging.

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CCTVs – Closed-Circuit Televisions

CPU – Central Processing Unit

CUDA – Compute Unified Device Architecture

GB – gigabyte

GPU – Graphical Processing Units

IEEE – Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers

mAP – mean Average Precision

RAM – Random Access Memory

RFID – Radio-frequency Identification

SSD – Solid State Drive

YAML – YAML Ain't Markup Language

YOLOv5 – You Only Look Once version five

3D – 3-dimensional

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and Context

We would all agree that without security, the element of being safe is jeopardized. Without safety, we consequently lose comfort and ease in our surrounding, of our items, our emotions and even lives.

Security measures are put in various places, from our homes, workplaces, shopping centres, religious centres, hospitals, on our roads and learning institutions for different reasons. The list is long, and the mentioned are just on our outside security(physically); we also have measures put in place to ensure we are ‘internally’ secure for instance counselling sessions for emotional security and even financial security. With all these, you do realize that we all in one way or another are encompassed with security measures. In this project, we will focus on security within our learning institutions.

There are different security measures put up in learning institutions to ensure the students learn in a convenient environment and their instructors teach in a conducive atmosphere. The practice has been fruitful and this is evident from how students and instructors perform alike, their retention in the institutions and even more as a result. The measures are put up for different purposes, for instance: closed-circuit televisions (CCTVs) which are more like the big man who is always on the lookout and you would not go against the institution’s rules on the camera, lest you be policed. There are the security guards who ensure security in the coming into and going out of one, into the institution; checking for any harmful items getting into the premise. Smoke detectors in the classrooms to ensure no smoking is done in the building and even detect when there is a fire outbreak. Metal detectors in the library to prevent any theft of the school books. These are the current security measures in place within our learning institution, Riara University.

1.2. Problem Statement

There are various mechanisms used for security purposes but are they secure?

On October 26, 2019, one of the desktop computers was stolen from one of the Riara labs never to be found again. Before that, a mouse and a keyboard had been stolen from the same lab. Mind you, we have metal detectors and several security guards, who do their work well. How many more items getaway and are not followed up? How many more breaches do we need to have before we realize there are loopholes in the current security systems? Some computer mouse are made up of rubber balls and not metal, are metal detectors enough?

Patikana focuses on getting images using machine learning by computer vision. The model will have an image, for instance in the lab, the model would have images of what the desktop computers look like. The model will then be instilled in a passage into the lab. In the case that an individual passes in possession of what resembles what is set in the system, the model will be able to raise an alarm.

There is equipment in place to enhance security measures, but most revolve around metal detection or reacting to what is around them for instance smoke detectors. Hence, the visual detection aspect in the supervised model. There are a few visual detectors in existence but a greater context. For example, detecting knives. Patikana will therefore localize the context and provide flexibility to have the model manipulatable with the environs.

1.3. Research Questions

Can items be more secure if visual detection is used in comparison to metal detection?

Can computer vision and human vision work simultaneously to improve each other's performance, in terms of securing items?

1.4. Relevance of the Research

There are always security risks, and no one needs to be worried about buying an expensive item with the fear that it could be stolen, without any trace.

The new insights that my research will bring onboard; having systems that are adaptable in local settings. There have been projects done on the efficacy, reliability and resiliency in computer vision for malware detection and research conditions, visual detection of knives in security

applications using active appearance models and Artificial Intelligence security cameras to combat mass shooters. The current systems are focused on dangerous items only but Patikana will also work with useful items to prevent stealing.

1.5. Objectives

1.5.1 General Objective

- i) To enhance security measures within a learning institution by reducing the rate at which items are lost in an institution.

1.5.2 Specific Objective

- i) To develop a computer vision model, Patikana, which will be able to identify an item when leaving a premise, that is not meant to leave.

1.6. Justification

The main driver of this project is to see the reduction of the rate of items disappearing without a trace. In this context to minimize, close to completely prevent the loss of electoral items from the computer laboratory. And, to develop a computer vision model that will detect illegal removal of items from a building.

1.7. Scope

The scope of this project will be on the security of items in a building within a learning institution, detecting the items as one exits the building.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Computer Vision

This is an area in deep learning that teaches machines to see, recognize and process images in a human-like manner. To see, the machines use numbers to process everything, including text and images. Each number denotes a particular location's pixel intensity. In order for the machine to learn, it is trained using as much data as possible and that's how it is able to see. As it learns, it begins to recognize patterns and make rules that will help it remember in future. The more it is trained, the better the machine gets with its recognition.

2.2. X-Ray Baggage Inspection

Mery et al. (2020) In their survey, the researchers were cognizant of the fact that adjustments have been made by development and research experts, on X-Ray testing to give the human operators in charge of manipulating the machine, a hand. Their paper reported on the current condition of how baggage is inspected, clearly pointing out the fields of research that had been looked at to enhance the automation of baggage inspection. The areas were namely: X-Ray energies, X-Ray multi-views and X-Ray computer vision algorithms. Consideration was given to X-Ray energies, because of the evidence they had, showing that multi-energy X-Ray testing had to be used during the characterization of the material. X-Ray multi-views, for their effectiveness in examining complex objects where one would seek total certainty to prevent misinterpretation. X-Ray computer vision algorithms, since there are various approaches in computer vision that can handle the plethora of existing problems in 3D object detection. Besides, the paper presented useful datasets that are publicly available and could be useful for training and testing. Notwithstanding, the general gaps were highlighted and the new areas viable for research put up.

X-Ray testing is a method that has been used to help in the detection of illegal/prohibited items as a result of the images of good quality of the items within a pack for example a bag. This technique has heightened the security standards of various public entrances like in airports, government buildings, event venues with large crowds etc. The system looks out for suspicious objects like knives, explosives, handguns that would be hidden inside the bags. However, in as much as there is a combination of ultrasound propagating ultrasonic waves, hyperspectral imaging capturing different points of the electromagnetic spectra and thermography determining the irradiated

temperature using infrared lights; the inspection is very complex and the human operator would still find it tedious and extremely hard to find to locate such items in cluttered bags (with occlusion and rotation problems). Even though some development has been made, human operators still play a big role in the manipulation of the baggage screening systems, which is a very monotonous process, strenuous with a high demand of one's concentration. After a long duration of the inspection, only a few objects that would present a threat are detected, putting into account that there are very different shapes and materials that would need to be recognized in a short period. Even with much training, one would not rub off the probability of the human operators making errors as their accuracy during the inspection is between eighty and ninety per cent.

Figure 1: Baggage inspection using computer vision

Source from: IEEE Xplore

In figure 1, the object (for example a bag) is irradiated from different angles with different X-Ray energies. Each block is usable depending on the application being used to define the different strategies in the solution. For instance, an application like knife detection could be implemented

by segmenting a mono-energy single view (represented by the black square). Or, follow a pattern recognition strategy (represented by red squares). Or, process a single mono-energy multiview, in the case of a cluttered bag (represented by green squares). Or, use corresponding information between the views (represented by blue squares). Or, process dual-energy X-Ray images to establish the material of single views (represented by magenta squares) and multi-views (represented by yellow squares). Or, solutions using active vision to find the next best projection (represented by cyan squares). For every strategy, the blocks that lack the mentioned colour square are not used.

The automated X-Ray testing was deemed less than ideal as a result of,

- i) Loss of generality; strategies created for one problem could be inefficient for the other.
- ii) Low accuracy; tradeoff existing between false positive and false negative rates.
- iii) Low robustness; solutions robust enough in specific cases only.
- iv) Low adaptiveness; a strategy designed for a particular purpose not adaptable in different conditions.

The paper identified three main areas of research that were related to the challenges, for example, energies, algorithms and views, with the taxonomy dubbed 3X-Strategy. Each solution corresponded to a point in the 3X-space defined as a combination of X-Ray energies (X_1), X-Ray computer vision algorithms (X_2) and X-Ray multi-views (X_3). In the inspection of the baggage, three factors were found impactful on detection, namely:

- i) Type of X-Ray image, dependent on the X-Ray energies used in the acquisition process of the image.
- ii) Point of view, dependent on whether or not other objects were superimposed over the target object, and the pose, which would also be affected by the rotation of the object.
- iii) The complexity of the image, dependent on the available number of objects present and their positioning inside the bag.

The factors were addressed using a 3X-strategy and it was clear that certain objects of interest required more than one X-Ray energy/view/simple algorithm.

In conclusion, the paper noted that despite the progress made in object recognition as a result of the modern computer vision techniques in X-Ray testing, many of the methods were not up to

standard with the existing complex problems in X-Ray imaging like noise, occlusion, acquisition and clutter among others. Hence the need to design new approaches that could support the operation of human inspectors. The computer vision method would then highlight the potential threat objects on the screen and allow the inspectors to make the final decision. There are still many gaps in existence in the work of baggage inspection, for instance; effective recognition techniques, pose difficulty, image complexity, throughput and (self) occlusion. The researchers believed that a solution had to efficiently put together X-Ray energies, computer vision algorithms and view using the 3X-strategy, which would then aid human inspectors to detect any prohibited items with a reasonable degree of probability. There was a finding that the introduction of techniques based on modern computer vision for X-Ray testing in baggage inspection was worthwhile but very slow as a result of the public and representative datasets constructed to train the detection models. The experts were then advised to label their data such as to define bounding boxes, make an annotation. It was also noted that there was no research work on imprecisely reconstructed 3Ds to allow for the object's recognition without measurement or characterization. For instance, in baggage inspection, one would not need to know the exact measurements of a knife or information related to it but would simply need to know whether it's a knife or a threat object.

In the screening of baggage, human security plays a major role and where inspection complexity is very high, the human operators are still needful. The research recognized that humans and machines working hand-in-hand is of the essence. The idea raised two questions:

- i) Can human vision be better/worse than human vision in particular cases? Do they have similar performance?
- ii) Can human vision and computer vision work simultaneously to improve each other's performances for instance, could humans be helped by machines or could one use human abilities to build better machine learning systems?

The research found that human vision and computer vision in recognition could mutually be beneficial to one another in the sense that the accuracy of human vision could be increased if computer vision algorithms could find potential parts with threat objects and the accuracy of computer vision be enhanced if new models were included based on human perception.

For further research, the team recommended the definition of standard evaluation protocols on public datasets to make fair comparisons to help in the easier determination of pros and cons through the evaluation of different strategies. And, new developments put in place as a trustworthy system to achieve a high level of trust by the users for example passengers, operators; meaning the system should be ethical, robust and lawful.

2.3. Feature Detection

Dong et al., (2020) In their paper, the researchers proposed a video-oriented cascaded intelligent face detection algorithm that would build the deep learning network by having multiple features cascaded, and advancing them layer by layer. The algorithm had good detection performance when it came to detecting images of single and multiple faces. The paper recognized the fact that the art of face recognition had become an important component of computer vision over the years and had been implemented in the area of public security in the early years. It had been largely used and known for its timely, intuitive, rich and accurate content. With the continual development in video monitoring, much information about the monitoring image had exceeded the effectiveness in the processing range of resources by humans. A gap was noted that there was a need for intelligent video analysis as the present systems could just monitor but not control by themselves. With face recognition, the team highlighted that they could extract and record the faces in the surveillance videos just in real-time, give an alarm and use the information that had been stored effectively. Consequently, this would help the security personnel as they dealt with the crisis hence minimizing false and missing alarms, and as such helping the checkpoint in dealing with attacks and emergencies. The system would easily solve the mentioned problems with the help of face recognition. It could use the technology of advanced artificial intelligence in the analysis of face detection to screen out suspects.

Detection of faces determines whether there exists a face in a dynamic or static image after some processing and analysis are done. There has been researching done on face detection but there are still some applications facing challenges on the same, hence the need to develop a technology on video face detection that could adapt to all presented circumstances. The introduction of the intelligent video retrieval technology could also unburden people from onerous and monotonous tasks as it used automatic digitization, video segmentation, voice recognition, keyframe extractions

and other technologies needful for the processing of images, pattern recognition, image understanding, computer vision and other fields. With analysis and preprocessing being automatically intelligent, the illogical and disordered monitoring of contents of the video like moving pedestrians, vehicles and people are looked into and only the information that is of relevance in the video automatically obtained. To help in the increasing speed of the computing, a cluster made is adopted to provide up to ten times higher analysis ability quickly, in real-time and is expandable based on the needs of the application. The video retrieval technology application in the monitoring of security is also founded on the technology, analysis of videos intelligently. It visually analyses the computer images by separating what's in the background and the goal in a scene of the camera. The intelligent video analysis technology would be used in separating what's in the background and the target in the scene and analyzes and tracks the goal in the scene of the camera. It would highly improve the efficiency rate in the retrieval and hitting of the monitoring video storage system's general mass.

Figure 2: How security monitoring works

Source from: IEEE Xplore

Figure 2 shows feature detection steps. A current image is compared with a known image of human face and if there's similarity it is recognized as a human face.

Currently, the technology collects faces in surveillance videos, obtains necessary information of the objects of interest in the video then based on the face information generates an index. From the image, the important personnel can watch the intentioned goal in the video that would have taken hours in just a short time, get to know the target in play and the available motion traces and clips of the target in the entire video. The face photos are input to be queried, the selected faces retrieved, parameters for example similarity set then the process of retrieval begins. At last, the resulting similarity of faces retrieved and displayed.

In conclusion, the team recognized that increasingly, enterprises are focusing on surveillance video products with face recognition. The system focuses on analysis in pre-warning of the video images in a collection but analysis afterwards leads to wastage in energy and manpower hence the need for the recognition of faces to lower the rate of crimes happening and consequently the maintenance in the society's stability and eventually the country. This would be made possible by a network in deep learning detection to detect single frame faces in videos. Layer by layers, the number of neurons would reduce in every hidden layer and as such have the size of the neurons in the network restricted. With the detection of skin color in the generation of key areas in the processing layer, the neural network's robustness is increased and still the amount of neurons decreased in every layer of the network. The network would initialize the network's parameters by training beforehand and using greedy learning in the prevention of multi-layer transfer of error, the resulting error from the final layer becomes so small that it adjusts the parameters of the network well and in essence improving the robustness alongside maintaining the learning of the network's global optimization.

The paper then proposed an algorithm on face detection based on the combination of multi models in deep learning. The idea would use feature vectors obtained from two types of models in the network for instance the factor of weight relevant in the whole feature network in addition to the network locally featured, obtaining a fixated value, input them and output as a network model for face comparison to distinguish through comparison of the network instead of fixing a factor of weight to deduce the similarity.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY/ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

3.1. System Analysis

This inculcates the studying of a procedure or business to derive its set goals and purposes, additionally creating systems and right procedures to enable them efficiently achieve the goals and purposes. (Lonnie, N.D)

This was an essential component in the development of my project as it was needful that I define the goals and purposes of my project and clearly outline the systems that propelled me to achieve them.

3.2. Stages in System Analysis

i) The gap in learning institution's security systems

There exist security measures implemented in our learning institutions but their efficiency is questionable. Despite the presence of measures for example smoke detectors, metal detectors, security guards and CCTVs, items still go missing and are unable to be traced. Each measure is beneficial but there is a gap between how much the systems and humans capture that is needful versus not needful.

ii) Patikana's requirement

The computer vision object detection model, Patikana was trained on given images, 778 images in a dataset, and was able to recognize more than 50% of the objects it had been trained on. The model was built on Google's Colaboratory notebook, with adjustments made on its python files using Pycharm.

iii) Requirement elicitation and feasibility study

Patikana's requirements were well researched. Previously, I had opted to use pre-trained YOLOv5 models but that was not efficient since the previous models had not been trained to detect desktops

and with that, I realised that Patikana needed to be custom trained for its object detection. From my feasibility study, I was able to define what I could achieve within the given time and available hardware and software.

iv) Model illustration of activities

Figure 3 is a model illustration of what Patikana entails using an activity diagram:

At its onset, patikana is trained, images are passed through Patikana. The model then detects the present classes, outputting them with confidence percentages. It then stops the activity.

Figure 3: Activity diagram of Patikana

3.3. Feasibility Study

This is a report that comprehensively examines the five frames of analysis in any given project. It covers four Ps which include; plan, process, power and people, notwithstanding its risks and constraints. Eventually, the end goal of the study was to determine whether the particular project should be continued, re-designed or discontinued. (Kenton, 2018)

Through this study, I realised what was workable in my project considering the needful versus available resources. Below are the six types of feasibility that I considered with regards to my project. These include; economic, schedule, technical, political, contractual and organizational feasibility.

3.3.1. Schedule Feasibility

This is the estimation of the duration that the system took to develop. The time given to bring the project to completion was three months. (BrightHubProjectManagement, N.D)

3.6. Gantt Chart

WEEKS	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
RESEARCH AND PROTOTYPE DRAFTING											
COLLECTING FACTS											
REPORT AND CODING											
EVALUATION											
FINAL REPORT											

Figure 4: Gantt Chart

Figure 4 shows an estimation of the time I took to bring this project to completion.

3.3.2. Technical Feasibility

This focused on the technical resources I had available and determined whether the technical resources were enough and that I had the right skill set to operate them. (Simplilearn, 2020)

Patikana needed a computing device, which I own. With the provisions by Google's colabratory, the model was majorly dependent on the notebook and not on the machine.

3.3.3. Economic Feasibility

This entails the financial assessment of the project's benefits that may be tangible or intangible and the capital one would need to establish the project. (BrightHubProjectManagement, N.D)

For Patikana, the software I used was open-source and did not incur a lot of money, as illustrated in table 1.

Table 1: Budget

RESOURCES	COST
PyCharm	Jet Brain's Student License: Free
Roboflow	Free Plan
Google Colabratory Notebook	Open Source
YOLO Object Detection Models	Open Source
Other Costs	Ksh. 70,000
TOTAL	Ksh. 70,000

3.3.4. Resource Feasibility

This entails the resources that would be needful for the successful development of the project. (BrightHubProjectManagement, N.D)

Patikana is a computer-based project and needed both hardware and software components. The hardware was an 8GB RAM laptop, 256GB SSD and Intel corei5 CPU. The software was Google's Colabratory, YOLOv5 object detection models, Roboflow and PyCharm.

3.4. Requirement Elicitation

This is the process of researching and finding out the system's requirement from customers, users and other stakeholders (Ramos, Kurts, John & Sons, 1997)

For Patikana, below are the techniques I used to identify the problems and requirements of the solution from the user community.

3.4.1. Requirement Gathering Methods

i) Personal experience

The incident that involved a computer disappearing from one of my school's computer laboratory, Riaru University, very much involved me. I had asked for the laboratory's key to access the room for a class we had, then we shifted the rooms but I did not remember to alert the security personnel to lock up the room. Two days after I was summoned and questioned on the same. Without any answers, all I was left with were questions such as were the current security measures within the institution good enough?

ii) Questionnaire

I then went ahead to the librarian to inquire about the kind of security system that was used close to the library's door to help in the detection of 'stolen' books. I found out the door frame had a metal detector that responded to RFID tags placed in the books. From this, I wondered whether a metal detector would work on all items. Are all items metallic, for them to be secured using metal detectors? Must there be the element of metal for the security of an item to be guaranteed?

iii) Secondary data

With automation being improved over the years, there is always research in this space. As such I was able to collect information on what other researchers have pointed out on the gaps in the current security measures and research, I got these problems consistently appearing:

- i) The current systems are still very much dependent on humans to operate in detecting threat object(s)/person(s). The systems can monitor but not fully control themselves.

- ii) The duty of having to follow through surveillance video / X-Ray Baggage Inspection systems is not only monotonous, onerous but also strenuous as the process requires their concentration that lasts for hours. As such, they are prone to miss the relevant object(s)/person(s) to be found out.

3.5. System Design

This is the process of pointing out the elements of a system; it defines, develops and designs systems to satisfy the specific needs and requirements presented. (The Economic Times)

3.5.1. Physical Design

This denoted how users were to input information in the system and how the user would get the information back, how the data is modelled then stored in the system, and finally how data moves through the system, is validated, secured and/or transformed while it is flowing through and out of the system. (The Economic Times)

Figure 5: Physical design of Patikana

3.5.2. Logical Design

This represents the inputs, outputs and data flow of the system. (The Economic Times)

In figure 6, there is an illustration of how the trained, tested and validated dataset from Roboflow undergoes through training, then images passed through it for detection and it finalizes by producing an output on which classes have been detected while the images are passed through the model, Patikana

In figure 7, the conceptual framework shows how the number of trainings for Patikana determine how accurate the model will be moderated by the size and variation of the images in the dataset. In that, the more the number of images and variations, the better the accuracy of the model.

Figure 6: Logical design of Patikana

Figure 7: Conceptual framework of Patikana

Figure 8 shows a block diagram of Patikana. The model acquires the image or video as passed through it. It preprocesses the image or video, segments it, extracts the available features, classifies them depending on the available classes in the image/video.

Figure 8: A block diagram of Patikana

CHAPTER FOUR: IMPLEMENTATION, TESTING AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Implementation:

I used YOLOv5 Pytorch Object Detection Model on Google Colaboratory notebook to create a customized computer vision model, Patikana. I settled on the notebook after I realised that the available pre-trained models, to be trained on PyCharm, had not been trained to detect desktops hence the need to create and train my own.

Google colaboratory was efficient as the platform can freely connect to Python 3 Google Compute Engine backend, which then provides a RAM of 12.72GB and a disk space of 68.40GB which are needful for the creation of the model. I also used Roboflow to annotate the images before training them in three classes: desktop, keyboard, mouse, and Pycharm in the modification of python files from YOLOv5 so that they are customized rightfully.

4.1.1 Hardware/Software Used:

My laptop was the only hardware I used with the Google colaboratory providing the essentials for the model. The software used was Google colaboratory notebook, PyCharm and Roboflow.

I chose Python as the programming language as it is more diverse with its machine learning packages as compared to other languages. Roboflow was my image annotation tool of choice because of its ease of use, and its ability to simplify the section of data labelling and model training.

4.2. How the System Works

Patikana is meant to be able to detect desktops, keyboards and mouse(s) to ensure they are always contained in their rightful places.

On Google colaboratory, the YOLOv5 Pytorch object detection model is first cloned from GitHub, where it's open-source. It then connects to the available GPUs supported by CUDA and displays the device properties of the specifically assigned GPU. A dataset with images previously annotated

on Roboflow is downloaded into the model, having been labelled in three classes: desktop, mouse, keyboard. To create the dataset, I downloaded photos from unsplash and pixabay as they offer quality photos for free. I then annotated by cropping the scope in which a particular item of either of the classes lay and then clicked on the right class, hence labelling it. The whole annotating process was done manually.

Figure 9: An example of Patikana’s annotated image on Roboflow

The new dataset loads, previously having been divided into training, validation and testing datasets in a ratio of 70:20:10. The recommended ratio is 80:20 when training and testing, with the assumption that validation is done during training but in this case, I did validation separately from the training set. The training set must have as many images as possible since that’s where the model learns. During each epoch, the model would be repeatedly trained on the data in the training set. The validation set is worked on simultaneously as the model is trained. The purpose of validation is to help curb overfitting which occurs when the model can detect an item that had been trained but cannot correctly detect one that was not in the training set. The test is used to test the model after the training process whether it can correctly detect the images. A YAML file, automatically created by Roboflow is then displayed in the colaboratory with the needful data, entailing values of the class and the configuration of the model. The model’s parameters are then defined using a yaml script, for instance, several anchors and classes, and every single layer. It then moves on to train the model by passing different arguments.

The model is trained, in 100 epochs, displaying but not limited to the GPU memory used, image sizes, mAPs. The training performance metrics and results are then saved to a log file, named YOLOv5s_results and a TensorBoard. The file with the results is then saved as a png as training completes. In the case that TensorBoard fails to work, graphs can alternatively be displayed. After the training, visualization is done for the data that has been trained to see training labels, images and augmentation effects. Ground truth training data is displayed then a ground truth training augmented training data. Lastly, the inference is run with the trained weights, and detection is done for a video or image as uploaded on the notebook.

Figure 8 shows an image from the computer laboratory at Riara University before detection and figure 9 shows an image of the same after detection. The bounding boxes on figure 9 show what the model has detected from the image, indicating what class the model thinks the image is and the values beside the name are the percentage in which the model is confident in its predictions. One can change the confidence levels they expect the model to detect the images but the recommended one is to have it at 50% since setting it too low gives the model a leeway to make more errors for instance it can detect a table to be a keyboard at a confidence level of 1% and setting the confidence level too high reduces the predictability rate since it would only output what it highly has confidence in its prediction.

Appendix 1 is an image of the graphs showing how the model performed during the training, validation and testing. The box graph is an imagery of a boxplot that visualizes the distribution of the given data in terms of maximum, minimum, median, third quartile and first quartile in the data set. The graph on objectness shows how probable it is that an object exists in the proposal's region of interest, essentially to tell how accurate the model is in its accuracy. The classification graph shows how populated the dataset is in the given classes. The precision graph displays the sum of retrieved images and relevant images over the number of retrieved results and the recall graph displays the sum of retrieved images and relevant images over the total relevant images, as is the case for our Patikana model. val Box, val Objectness and val Classification mean the same as the previous explanations for box, objectness and classification respectively, except that this is solely on the validation dataset. mAP@0.5 shows the model's mean average precision of at 50 percent while mAP@0.5:0.95 shows the model's mean average precision in the range of 50 percent and

95 percent. Appendix 2 shows the ground truth on the data that had been trained, showcasing how the model performed in testing having been trained. It brings together the resulting images on how the model performed in detecting images during testing. Appendix 3 shows the detection process and how the video is run inference and output stored after detection. It displays the cell that was run and how during detection the model segments the video into frames so it can run through each frame and detect correctly.

Figure 10: An image from Riara University's computer laboratory

Figure 11: A resulting image after detection in the computer laboratory

4.3. Testing:

This was done to check if the built model was able to accomplish what was expected to have it produce, ensuring the model has no defect.

I used two types of testing for my system: functionality testing and interface testing.

4.3.1. Functionality Testing

I tested whether the system was able to accomplish its set functionalities.

Patikana's main function was to detect desktop, keyboard and mouse. I had an inference run on a video after training the model and it was able to detect more than 50% images of the set classes, hence passed the test.

4.3.2. Interface Testing

Through interface testing, I was able to determine the model's components can pass data and control them correctly passing data to each other.

Patikana passed the test as it could automatically achieve what was expected from one cell to another.

4.3.3. Performance Testing

In this testing, different metrics were measured: mean average precision at 50%, mean average precision varying from 50% to 95%, precision, recall, box_loss, cls_loss(classification loss) and obj_loss(objectness loss) were tested. It was fairly well to note that the mean average precision graph was increasing since that showed that the model became more accurate at 50% and when it varied from 50% to 95%. The precision metric showed whether whatever had been predicted was really correct. From the graph, the model's precision rate increased but at some points it declined and then increased. The declining, especially on a high rate is not recommended hence the model needs more training. The recall metric shows how many of the correct images were correctly detected, and in this case the graph went up which means as the model was being trained, it got better in identifying the images of the set classes. The graphs on losses show how erroneous the model was with its prediction, and since the losses on the box, classification and objectness are decreasing, it signifies that the model got better in its detection as it got trained.

4.4. Analysis

During analysis, it was realised that the model was able to correctly detect at least 50% of the images that it had previously been trained on in the video.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION, EVALUATION AND FURTHER WORK

5.1. Objectives Attained

Patikana was able to detect the given classes: desktop, keyboard, mouse.

Besides, the system can give an evaluation of its performance hence ease to adjust it for better performance.

5.2. Further Work

There is so much room for improvement on Patikana:

- i) The model should be incorporated with an IoT system so that once a particular item is detected, an alarm rings to get the attention of the security and lab technician.
- ii) Patikana has currently been run on video and images but it could be adjusted for use in real-time. It can do that, and once incorporated with the X-ray baggage cameras, it will be a seamless activity of monitoring equipment.
- iii) With more usage of Patikana, the model will get more intelligent hence creating room for expansion or usage in any other capacity.

5.3. Challenges Faced During Development

There were various varying challenges:

Google colabatory would disconnect after some time and one had to restart runtime which then meant restarting the whole system from start to finish. The notebook would also delete uploaded files once runtime was refreshed, so then one had to constantly upload the files to be detected. In addition to these, the notebook would not allow detection on large files hence limiting the uploaded video(s) to less than a minute. The format of the video being uploaded would also output errors depending on how efficient the notebook finds it.

Roboflow did not give room for tilted annotation and the available type led to strict annotation in only straight-lined boxes. The software also did not allow more than 1000 images for a dataset in the free plan, which then limited the number of images I would train the model on. Even after annotating, the bounding boxes were not all saved with the given details, some values were missing.

5.4. Conclusion

The world is fast-changing with data being the new oil and automation of the big buzzword. As we are all aware, inevitable to us is change. We either transform with it or it overtakes us. It is in the same lenses that I'd admonish that computer vision be looked into in ways that would be useful and increase productivity in addition to the human vision.

Patikana is one of the steps into enhancing the security measures of the current systems, as the system becomes intelligent, even more of its activities will be automated.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: TensorBoard visualization of Patikana's results

Appendix 2: Ground truth on augmented training data

